

Turnover Intention the Implication of Burnout and Unstable Employment

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 30 July 2022	Turnover intention, which can be brought on by a variety of factors such as severe work stress or unstable environmental conditions, is the desire to move but has not yet taken the realization step. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of: 1) Unstable employment on turnover intention. 2) Unstable employment on Burn out and 3) Burn out on Turnover intention. The data collection method used in this study was through a questionnaire. The research population is the employees of PT. Japfa Comfeed Indonesia Tbk with a total of 40 employees. The research sample is a saturated sample. Data were analyzed using PLS. The results showed that: 1) Unstable employment had a significant positive effect on turnover intention. 2) Unstable employment has a significant positive effect on Burn out. 3) Burn out has a significant positive effect on turnover intention. The results also show that unstable employment has a greater influence on turnover intention, this shows that not everyone thinks that people's discomfort at work can reduce a person's work motivation, causing someone to want to leave his job.
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INTRODUCTION

Today, there are a growing number of complicated factors influencing employee turnover (Lee et al., 2010). Employees' purpose to leave the organization in search of a better job than their current one is known as their turnover intention. (Arshadi & Damiri, 2013); (Azeez et al., 1993). Employees who have the intention to quit the organization voluntarily have this desire, which is known as turnover intention. (Tnay et al., 2013). Numerous things, such as desiring to receive more money or having family issues, can cause this desire. Voluntary or involuntary turnover intention is possible. (Hussein Alkahtani, 2015). Belete (2018), Role conflict, burnout, and a precarious job have a favorable and significant impact on the intention to leave a job. When the terms "intention to quit" and "turnover intention" are used interchangeably in literature, it means that the employee intends to leave their position as soon as a job opportunity arises or in the near future (Balogun et al., 2013). The possibility that a person may quit their current employment is referred to as their turnover intention (Belete, 2018). Turnover intention, according to research, is the movement of workers within the labor market between different organizations, professions, and positions, as well as between employment and unemployment (Dwesini, 2019).

The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of: 1) Unstable employment on turnover intention. 2) Unstable employment on Burn out and 3) Burn out on Turnover intention. The inconsistent findings of earlier investigations

were the impetus for the current study. (Pauline E. Ngo-Henha, 2017); (Ivanovic et al., 2020) discovered that one of the elements that may impact turnover intention is burnout. Employees who are psychologically and physically exhausted are more likely to consider leaving their current position. Nevertheless, in a research by Arif et al., (2018) burnout was found to have negative impact on auditor intention to leave, although it did make things more difficult at work.

Unstable Employment

Aldiasajjad & Suwarsi (2021), describes unstable employment as a psychological state where an individual exhibits feelings of uncertainty or unease as a result of changes in their environment (perceived impermanence). Wang et al., (2015), Employees who have unstable employment suffer from the mental condition of believing their jobs are in danger yet being helpless to do action. Results of Hariyonyoto et al., (2019), research, unstable employment has a positive effect on turnover intention. Suarka (2020) burn out and unstable employment affect turnover intention. Balogun et al., (2013), Job insecurity has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Rhee et al., (2020), job insecurity had a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Çınar et al., (2014), shows that unstable employment has a positive effect on turnover intention. From the statement above, it can be formulated the research

“Turnover Intention the Implication of Burnout and Unstable Employment”

hypothesis H1: There is an effect of Unstable employment on turnover intention.

Burnout

Stress at work is a prevalent aspect of contemporary living (Arshadi & Damiri, 2013). An extreme amount of work stress can lead to burnout (Kim & Lee, 2009); (Lu & Gursoy, 2016). Burnout is typically seen negatively. (Jung et al., 2012). When presented with opportunities, restrictions, or demands that seem excessive or outside the scope of their capabilities, people can feel burnout. Burnout is directly linked to the extreme expectations and constraints faced by workers. Ratnasari, (2016), Role conflict in the workplace significantly influences the likelihood of turnover intention (Soelton et al., 2020). studies carried out by (Lu & Gursoy, 2016); discovered how burnout affected employee turnover intention and work satisfaction. According to research findings by Jung et al., (2012) menyatakan bahwa burn out berpengaruh positif pada turnover intention. Cho & Lewis, (2012) Turnover intention is impacted by burnout. Burnout has generally been linked to a range of negative reactions to the job, such as job unhappiness, a lack of organizational commitment, and a high and high job turnover intention (Lu & Gursoy, 2016). From the statement above, the research hypothesis H2 can be formulated: There is an effect of Unstable employment on Burn out.

H3: There is an effect of Burn out on turnover intention.

Turnover Intention

Numerous studies have demonstrated that workplace pressures can cause mental, bodily, and behavioral stress reactions such as burnout, depression, and psychosomatic illnesses (Houkes et al., 2001). Workplace contentment and self-esteem are greatly harmed by job stress. It was established that turnover experience had a moderating influence while self-esteem had a somewhat mediating effect. It is critical to shed new light on the functions of self-esteem among factors affecting job satisfaction (Yang et al., 2016). (Silaban & Syah, 2018) stated that employees who have the desire or intention to pursue another employment as a substitute in a different organization are said to have turnover

intention. Turnover has a negative effect on organizational expenditures associated with hiring, selecting, and training new employees. (Alatawi, 2017).

METHODS

Research of this kind is quantitative. The 40 employees of PT. Japfa Comfeed Indonesia Tbk who make up the research population. A saturated sample is used in the investigation. A Likert scale is utilized as the measurement method. Unstable employment, burnout, and turnover intention are the research factors. the term "unstable employment indicator" Hariyonyoto et al., (2019), which includes: 1) the significance of work for the individual; 2) the degree to which employees perceive threats; 3) the degree to which threats are likely to materialize and affect the overall work of the individual; 4) the degree to which the individual perceives interest in particular events; and 5) the degree to which the job is likely to be threatened in the coming year. the term "burn out indicator" Srinadi & Supartha (2015) consisting of; 1) Task demands, 2) Role demands and 3) Interpersonal demands. The Turnover Intention indicator refers to Srinadi & Supartha (2015) consisting of: 1) leaving thoughts, 2) looking for a new employment, and 3) wanting to quit the company in the near future.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The outer model and inner model were used to assess the study's findings. The outer model, also known as the measurement model, is a stage used to assess a construct's reliability and validity. The Inner model investigates if the independent and dependent variables have any influence on one another.

Evaluasi Outer Model

Table 1 displays the results of the outer model test. Table 1's statistics indicate that the outer loading value yields a value greater than 0.70. These findings suggest that every statement indicator is either valid or meets convergent validity requirements.

Table 1. Outer Loading Value

Variable	Item	Outer Loading	Valid/Invalid
Unstable employment (X1)	X1.1	0,988	Valid
	X1.2	0,946	Valid
	X1.3	0,970	Valid
Burnout (Y1)	Y1.1	0,988	Valid
	Y1.2	0,970	Valid
	Y1.3	0,970	Valid
Turnover Intention (Y2)	Y2.1	0,950	Valid
	Y2.2	0,700	Valid
	Y2.3	0,966	Valid

Source: Primary data processed (2021)

The Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha values can be seen in table 2.

“Turnover Intention the Implication of Burnout and Unstable Employment”

Table 2. Composite Reliability Value and Cronbach Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha	Reliabel/Unrelia bel
Unstable employment (X1)	0,988	0,977	Reliabel
Burnout (Y1)	0,984	0,978	Reliabel
Turnover Intention (Y2)	0,914	0,848	Reliabel

Source: Primary data processed (2021)

The reliability test outcomes can be seen from composite reliability and cronbach alpha. All of the constructs in this investigation are trustworthy, as shown by Table 2's

composite reliability value, which is over 0.70.

Evaluasi Inner Model

In Figure 1. shows the Structural Model of the Inner Model

Figure 1. Structural Model of Inner Model

Significant effect of Unstable Employment on Turnover Intention.

Hypothesis 1 (H1) which states that unstable employment has a significant positive effect on turnover intention. So hypothesis 1 which states that job insecurity has an effect on turnover intention is accepted. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by (Hariyonyoto et al., 2019) shows that Unstable employment has a significant positive effect on turnover intention. As employee uncertainty grows, workers will become more eager to hunt for job at other organizations (Saputro, 2016). Whereas Hanafiah (2014), According to the claim that unstable employment has a positive link with turnover intention, unstable job status and unpredictably fluctuating income levels will raise turnover intention. Qazi *et al.* (2015) Additionally, it was noted that there is a positive correlation between unstable employment and turnover intention, with the desire to leave being higher the more unstable work is seen to be by the employees. Qazi *et al.* (2015) Furthermore, it was noted that there is a positive correlation between work insecurity and turnover intention, with the desire to leave the organization increasing as job insecurity among employees rises. The inability of employees to continue their positions in threatened working conditions will enhance employees'

desire to change occupations, it can therefore be stated that unstable employment is one of the elements that has a positive effect on turnover intention.

Unstable employment has a significant impact on burnout.

According to Hypothesis 2 (H2), Burn out is positively and significantly impacted by unstable employment. It is considered as a possibility that insecure employment has a favorable and notable impact on burnout. This demonstrates that the premise is correct. The findings of this research are consistent with (Aldiassajjad & Suwarsi, 2021) It demonstrates that Burn out is positively impacted by unstable employment. Excessive stress at work may be made worse by anxiety and concern about losing a long-term career. Similarly, research findings Kurniadi (2016) also implies the results that Burn out has a significant impact on work stress. Based on the respondents' answers obtained from the results of the distribution of the questionnaire which includes 3 statements with the highest average score, namely the question "The success of other employees inspires them to develop themselves. This shows that employees make the success rate between employees an inspiration for every work partner in the company.

Burnout has a significant impact on turnover intentions.

Burnout is hypothesized to have a positive and significant impact on turnover intention in Hypothesis 3 (H3). The idea that burnout has a positive and significant impact on turnover intention is accepted. The findings of this investigation are consistent with (Lu & Gursoy, 2016); (Houkes et al., 2001) Burn out has a positive effect on turnover intention, excessive pressure and nervous tension make employees think of leaving the organization. (Kim & Stoner, 2008) demonstrates that employee turnover intention is positively impacted by burnout; a higher perception of burnout will lead to a higher intention to quit. Similar conclusions were reached by (Jung et al., 2012), On the intention to turnover, burn out has a considerable favorable impact. Study (Ivanovic et al., 2020) shows that burn out has a positive relationship with turnover intention, with increasing burn out the intention of company employees to change jobs is increasing. Study (Soelton et al., 2020) Additionally demonstrates the link between burnout and the intention to leave an employer; if an employee has burnout and does not have a good way to deal with it, it will result in the employee wanting to leave. The more excessive work stress and pressure that employee experiences at work, the more likely they are to consider quitting the organization. It can therefore be stated that burn out is one of the factors that has a favorable effect on turnover intention. The findings of this research contradict by Arif et al., (2018)

CONCLUSION

This study gives the results that: 1) Unstable employment has a significant effect on turnover intention. The inability of employees to maintain their jobs in threatened working conditions will increase the desire of employees to change jobs. 3) Unstable employment has a significant effect on Burn out. Unstable organizational conditions in the organization caused by internal and external factors can trigger excessive stress for employees 3) Burn out has a significant effect on turnover intention. The more excessive work stress at work, it triggers employees to think about leaving the company. The more pressure in heavy work will trigger employees to think about leaving the company.

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